

Enhancing Knee Injury Assessment: The Synergy between Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Arthroscopic Correlation

Krishnamurthy Rajendra Kushbu Sony

Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Shri Sathya Sai Medical College & Research Institute (SSSMCRI), Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth University (Deemed to be University)

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Krishnamurthy Rajendra Kushbu Sony

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: The accurate assessment of knee joint injuries is paramount in orthopedic medicine to facilitate effective treatment strategies and optimal patient care. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has emerged as a pivotal diagnostic tool, offering detailed anatomical insights without invasive procedures. However, the standalone utility of MRI may sometimes be limited in providing a comprehensive understanding of knee injuries. Combining MRI with arthroscopic correlation has gained recognition to overcome this limitation, offering a synergistic approach for precise diagnosis and treatment planning.

Methodology: In this prospective study conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Chengelpet district, Tamil Nadu, 42 patients with traumatic knee injuries underwent MRI evaluation followed by arthroscopic examination. The MRI protocol included various sequences to assess different knee structures comprehensively. The MRI findings were meticulously correlated with arthroscopic results, and diagnostic parameters were computed.

Result: Our study revealed a male predominance (76%) among the participants, consistent with existing literature on knee injuries. ACL tear was the most prevalent abnormality detected on MRI, followed by joint effusion. Medial meniscal injury was the predominant meniscal pathology, with grade 3 tears involving the posterior horn of the medial meniscus frequently observed. Complete ACL tears were more common than partial tears.

Discussion: These findings underscore the clinical significance of integrating MRI with arthroscopic correlation for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning in knee injuries. The high prevalence of ACL tears, joint effusion, and medial meniscal injuries highlights the importance of tailored management strategies. This integrated approach facilitates a comprehensive understanding of knee pathology, ultimately optimizing patient outcomes.

Keyword: MRI, Assessment, Knee injury.

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Introduction

The assessment of knee joint injuries is a critical aspect of orthopedic medicine, as accurate diagnosis lays the foundation for effective treatment strategies and patient care. In recent years, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has emerged as a powerful tool in the evaluation of knee injuries, offering detailed anatomical information without the need for invasive procedures. However, the utility of MRI in isolation can sometimes be limited, as it may not always provide a complete understanding of the extent or nature of the injury.

To address this limitation, there has been increasing recognition of the value of combining MRI findings with arthroscopic correlation. Arthroscopy allows for direct visualization of intraarticular structures, enabling orthopedic surgeons to confirm and further characterize abnormalities identified on MRI. By integrating the complementary

information provided by these two modalities, clinicians can achieve a more comprehensive understanding of knee pathology, leading to more accurate diagnoses and improved treatment planning. [1]

The aim of the study is to explore the role of magnetic resonance imaging in the evaluation of knee joint injuries and highlight the importance of its synergy with arthroscopic correlation. Through a review of relevant literature and clinical examples, we aim to elucidate the benefits of this integrated approach and its implications for orthopedic practice. Additionally, we will discuss current trends and advancements in both MRI technology and arthroscopic techniques that further enhance the diagnostic capabilities in assessing knee injuries.

Methodology

A prospective study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Chengelpet district, Tamil Nadu, focusing on 42 patients presenting with a history of traumatic knee injury. Patients aged 18 years and above, with recent or old knee trauma, were eligible for inclusion in the study. Exclusion criteria encompassed individuals with infective or post-operative knee joint issues, those with implants, and any patients for whom MRI was contraindicated. Each of the 42 patients underwent MRI assessment of the knee joint followed by subsequent arthroscopic examination.

During MRI, patients were positioned supine with a 15-20 degree external rotation of the knee and 5-10 degrees of flexion, facilitating optimal visualization of the anterior cruciate ligament in sagittal images. Neutral positioning of the knee was adopted for coronal images. The MRI protocol entailed the acquisition of PD Fat sat axial, coronal, and sagittal images, as well as T1 TSE Sagittal, STIR Sagittal and axial, T2 FSE sagittal, T2 fat sat sagittal, and GRE Sagittal sequences. T2 Weighted Proton density images with fat suppression were routinely employed to assess fluid, bone marrow hyperemia, and articular cartilage, while STIR images were utilized for identifying bone contusions.

Image analysis involved rigorous criteria: a meniscal tear was classified as grade 3 signal intensity, with intrameniscal signal extending unequivocally to an articular surface, and the two-slice-touch rule was applied, requiring increased signal touching the articular surface on at least two slices to diagnose a tear. Partial tears of the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) were identified by abnormal signal intensity within the ligament or wavy appearance of intact fibers on sagittal and coronal images.

Complete ACL tears were diagnosed if all fibers were disrupted or if the ligament was entirely invisible on MRI. Standard criteria for signal in homogeneity were applied to diagnose other abnormalities such as ligament tears and bone contusions.

Results

The research cohort comprised 42 patients with a history of knee joint trauma, all of whom underwent arthroscopic evaluation.

The MRI findings were meticulously compared with the arthroscopic results, and various diagnostic parameters including sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive value, positive predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy were computed.

Table 1: Socio demographical distribution of study participants

S.no	Age group	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total
1.	18 – 20	3 (9%)	-	3 (7%)
2.	21 – 30	13 (41%)	2 (20 %)	15 (36%)
3.	31 – 40	8 (25%)	6 (60%)	14 (33%)
4.	41 – 50	5 (16%)	1 (10%)	6 (14%)
5.	51 – 60	2 (6%)	1 (10%)	3 (8%)
6.	Above 61	1 (3%)	-	1 (2%)
Total		32(76%)	10(24%)	42 (100%)

Of the 42 patients enrolled, 32 were male and 10 were female, indicating a male predominance of approximately 76%, as outlined in Table 1.

The analysis revealed that the most prevalent abnormality detected on MRI was ACL tear, observed in approximately 30 patients (73%), followed by joint effusion, which accounted for 52% of cases, as demonstrated in Table 2. Medial

meniscal injury was the most common among meniscal pathologies, affecting 8 patients (19%). Complete ACL tears were more frequent, observed in up to 21 cases among cruciate ligament injuries.

Among the 21 patients with meniscal injuries, grade 3 tears involving the posterior horn of the medial meniscus were frequently encountered, affecting 8 patients.

Table 2: MRI assessment

MRI Assessment	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
ACL tear	30	71%
PCL tear	6	14%
Lateral collateral Ligament	4	10%
Medial collateral Ligament	10	24%
Joint effusion	22	52%
Bone contusion	6	14%
Medial meniscal injury	8	19%
Lateral meniscal injury	3	7%

Discussion

The findings of this study underscore several noteworthy observations regarding knee joint injuries among the patient population studied. Firstly, the predominance of male patients, constituting approximately 76% of the cohort, aligns with existing literature documenting a higher incidence of knee injuries among males compared to females. This gender-based disparity may be attributed to various factors including differences in anatomy, biomechanics, and participation in sports activities. [2] The higher proportion of male participants highlights the need for tailored preventive strategies and targeted interventions to address this demographic.

The most prevalent abnormality identified on MRI was anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) tear, affecting approximately 73% of patients. This finding is consistent with prior research indicating ACL tears as one of the most common knee injuries, particularly among young athletes involved in pivoting sports. [3] The high incidence of ACL tears emphasizes the clinical significance of accurate diagnosis and prompt management to prevent long-term complications such as instability and cartilage damage. Joint effusion emerged as another frequent abnormality, observed in 52% of cases. Joint effusion, characterized by the accumulation of fluid within the knee joint, is often associated with acute trauma and inflammatory conditions. [4] Its detection on MRI underscores the importance of evaluating for concomitant intra-articular pathology in patients presenting with knee joint injuries.

Among meniscal pathologies, medial meniscal injury was predominant, affecting 19% of patients. This finding aligns with previous studies reporting a higher prevalence of medial meniscal tears compared to lateral tears, possibly due to greater biomechanical stress on the medial compartment of the knee during weight-bearing activities. [5]

The frequent occurrence of grade 3 tears involving the posterior horn of the medial meniscus highlights the clinical significance of accurately characterizing meniscal injuries to guide appropriate treatment strategies, including conservative management versus surgical intervention. [6]

Complete ACL tears were more common than partial tears, with up to 21 cases identified in this

study. Complete ACL tears are often associated with significant functional impairment and instability, necessitating surgical reconstruction in many cases to restore knee joint stability and prevent subsequent damage to other intra-articular structures. [7] Overall, the findings of this study provide valuable insights into the epidemiology and patterns of knee joint injuries among the studied population. The high prevalence of ACL tears, joint effusion, and medial meniscal injuries underscores the importance of comprehensive diagnostic evaluation using MRI, followed by appropriate management tailored to the specific pathology encountered.

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